

DATE OF BIRTH: 15.08.64, Copenhagen.

EDUCATION

MD (University of Copenhagen),	1991
D.Sc. (University of Copenhagen),	1994
Professor (University of Copenhagen),	2003

EMPLOYMENT

Professor, Chief Surgeon, Dept. of Surgery, Herlev Hospital, University of Copenhagen.

SCIENTIFIC WORK**Thesis (DSc):** "Late postoperative episodic and constant hypoxaemia – mechanisms and clinical implications". University of Copenhagen, 1994.**1099 publications:****1008 peer reviewed scientific articles****59 book chapters****32 books****H-index (January 2026):****102 (meaning that 102 papers were cited 102 times or more)**<http://scholar.google.dk/citations?user=FhVE85IAAAJ>

	Alle	Siden 2021
Henvisninger	45027	16273
h-index	102	60
i10-indeks	536	338

>500 scientific lectures as "invited visiting professor" or at national or international congresses/symposia.**TEACHING: Has been teacher at >150 postgraduate courses.**

Scientific tutor (past and present) for

- 107 Masters projects
- 83 student research fellows (one year program)
- 7 DMSc candidates
- 59 PhD students

Official opponent at 26 PhD and 5 DSc defences**Honorary prizes:**

- Hede Nielsen Prize 1997
- Olympus Prize 1999
- NC Nielsen Prize 2002
- Johan Quentin and wife's Prize 2003
- Society for theoretical and practical therapy, Gold medal 2003
- Lundbeck Foundation, young investigator prize 2003
- DGS honorary prize 2005
- Royal Copenhagen Medical Society Research Prize 2021
- Lippmann prize 2025

Honorary Fellow of the Royal College of Surgeons of England, 2004-2013**Fellow of the American College of Surgeons, from 2005****Assistant editor, Ugeskrift for Læger and Danish Medical Journal, 2002-2008****Editor-in-chief, Ugeskrift for Læger (www.ugeskriftet.dk), 2008-2015****Editor-in-chief, Danish Medical Journal (www.danmedj.dk), 2008-2015****International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (www.icmje.org), 2008-2015****Associate editor, Scandinavian Journal of Surgery, 2016-2018****Co-ordinating Editor, The Cochrane Collaboration, from 2018****Senior Editor, The Cochrane Collaboration, from 2024****Editorial Board member, Laparoscopic Surgery, from 2020****President, Royal Copenhagen Medical Society, 2012-2014****Chairman, Danish National Hernia database, 2009-2011****Rated #1 top-rated expert in the World on hernia (<https://expertscape.com/ex/hernia>)**